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Şenkal KİLECI

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New Epitaphs from Cibyra and Gölhisar - III

Kibyra ve Gölhisar'dan Yeni Mezar Yazıtları - III

Şenkal KİLECI *

Abstract: This study introduces five new epitaphs of cylindrical form found in Cibyra and the Gölhisar, district of Burdur. The four of the stelae are mostly well preserved. The fourth one has a missing part on the front upper part with its inscription and is kept the excavation house which was brought there from the garden of the Governmental Building of the province in Gölhisar. Other three stelae (nos. 1, 2, 3) are found during an archaeological drilling in front of the arch, on the pavement of the main street, and they can be seen at the entrance of the stadium. The last one (no. 5) is found on the western side of the odeium and stands now in the stone field in front of the theatre. All the inscriptions are dated from the style of lettering employed. The characterization of the letters is known from the inscriptions found at Cibyra of which the dates are known.

Keywords: Epitaph, Stelae, Cibyra, Gölhisar

Öz: Buradaki çalışma Burdur iline bağlı Gölhisar ilçesi içerisinde yer alan yayımlanmamış beş mezar stelini konu edinmektedir. Bunlardan dört tanesi iyi derecede korunmuş olup dördüncünün ön üst kısmı yazıtıyla birlikte kırık ve noksandır. Bu stel kazı evinde korunmakta olup Hükümet Konağı'nın bahçesinden getirilmiştir. Diğer üç stel (no. 1, 2, 3) tak ile ana cadde arasında yapılan sondaj çalışmaları sırasında bulunmuştur. 5 no'lu stel ise odeion'un batısındaki yamaçta bulunmuş olup bugün tiyatro önünde yer alan taş tarlasındadır. Burada sunulan tüm yazıtlar harf karakterleri baz alınarak tarihlendirilmiştir. Bu karakterler kentte daha önce kayıt altına alınmış ve tarihi belli yazıtlara endeksli şekilde belirlenmiştir.

Anahtar sözcükler: Mezar Steli, Stel, Kibyra, Gölhisar

1. Epitaph of Eunoia and Eperastos

A cylindrical epitaph made of marble. The stele can be seen at the entrance to the stadium. On top of it is a high profile of 13 cm. Below this is a ridge and another profiled area. The body of the stele begins where the second profile area ends, and is divided into three parts, in size ordered from top to bottom, 21 x 29 x 23 cm. The first part, which is 21 cm high, carries a three-line-inscription carved in ancient Greek, which is well preserved well and legible. The second part is 28 cm high and is carved slightly deeper than the adjacent upper and lower bands. After the third band is the lower part which is also profiled. The Sigma is square C, and the alpha has a broken bar.

Findspot: In front of the arch, on the pavement of the main street.

Dimensions: h.: 117 cm; d.: 52 cm; l.h.: 2.8-3 cm.

Date: II-IIIrd cent. A.D. (from the lettering).

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Ἐπέραστος Κόμ[ω]-
 2 νος Εὐνοία τῆ γ[υ]-
 ναικὶ καὶ ἑαυτῷ ζῶν.

*Eperastos, son of Komon,
 (set this up) while living,
 for himself and his wife
 Eunoia.*

L.1: The name *Eperastos* meaning “lovely” is here attested in Kibyrtis for the first time. This name has been recorded in Asia Minor thirteen times and is mostly found on the western coastal side of Anatolia, starting from Bithynia, all the way through Mysia, Ionia, Caria and Lycia. It is mostly found in Ionia, particularly in Didyma and Miletus, and one is also attested in Smyrna¹. For the other coastal regions, the name attested once in Bithynia, Mysia, Caria and Lycia². All but two are dated to the I-IInd century A.D., the ones in Nikaia and Cnidus are dated to a wider time span, to the Roman Imperial Period. The feminine form of *Eperastos* is Ἐπεράστα (= *Eperasta*) recorded at Termessos³.

LL. 1-2: The name *Komon* is before attested both from Kibyrtis and Pisidia, for details see *LGPN VC*. The name of *Komon*’s wife, *Eunoia*, is before unknown for Kibyra. However, this name has been before recorded in Tyana, Derbe and Pisidian Antiochia, see *LGPN VC*.

2. Epitaph of Naso

A cylindrical epitaph made of marble. The stele can be seen at the entrance to the stadium. The top is carved a bit higher. Then comes the profiled part in approx. 17 cm high. The body is divided into three bands like the first stele, in sizes, ordered from top to bottom, 29 x 40 x 30 cm. The first part carries a five-line-inscription carved in ancient Greek. The inscription is mostly well preserved and legible. The missing parts are eroded. The lower part is also profiled. The Alpha is written with a broken bar.

Findspot: In front of the arch, on the pavement of the main street.

Dimensions: h.: 127 cm; d.: 62 cm; l.h.: 3.2-4 cm.

Date: II-IIIrd cent. A.D. (from the lettering).

¹ For *Eperastos* at Miletus see *Milet* VI,3 1168; 1506; *Miletus* 14; at Didyma: *Didyma* 327; 328; 332; 376; 447; at Smyrna: *Smyrna* 502.

² For *Eperastos* at Nikaia in Bithynia see *Ilznik* 81; at Kyzikos in Mysia see *IMT Kyz Kapu Dağ* 1455; at Cnidus in Caria see *Knidos* 118; at Tlos in Lycia see *TAM* II 599.

³ *TAM* III,1 902.

- [Αρ]τεμίδωρος Ῥού-
 2 φου [Ρ]οῦφος Νασῶ
 Πανκράτους τῆ γυ-
 4 [ν]αίκι μνήμης ἔνεκα
 [κα]ὶ αὐτῷ ζῶντι Ϝ

Artemidoros Rufus, son of Rufus, (set this up) while living, in memory of his wife Naso, daughter of Pankrates, and for himself.

LL. 1-2: Artemidoros has a second name which is in Latin, Rufus, and he carries his father's name. The name Artemidoros means "given by Artemis", therefore it is a theophoric name. This name is well known throughout the Hellenic world starting from the Vth century B.C. until the Byzantine Period, and has been attested 1702 times. This is the third time this name has been recorded in Cibyra, see *IKibyra* 57 and 275. The Latin name *Rufus* has also been attested at Cibyra before, see *IKibyra* 160.

L. 2: The name *Naso* is a female name attested before in Kibyra, *IKibyra* 287. This name is written in the nominative case as Νασῶ. T. Corsten had accepted this name in the nominative case as Νασον, but the latest studies show that this name's nominative case is as was shown before, see *LGPN* VC.

L. 3: Πανκράτης or Πανκράτης. The name Pankrates is recorded in Cibyra eleventh times, mostly written with /νκ/ instead of /γκ/. And the genitive form is attested mostly as ending in -ου, however in *IKibyra* 363 it is written with the ending -ους. For these records see *IKibyra* 42A, 44A, 51, 214, 300, 312, 363, Kileci 2019, 343 no. 1; Alten-Güler 2020, 3 no. 4 and see also here no. 4.

3. Epitaph of Enas

A cylindrical epitaph made of marble. The stele can be seen at the entrance to the stadium together with the first two epitaphs. The top is cut but rough, and there is a little conical hole in the center around 0.045 m in diameter. The upper and the lower parts are profiled resembling a cyma. Beginning from the right to the back upper part, a large part of it is broken and missing. The body part is also divided into three bands like the first two stelae, in size ordered from top to bottom, 35x47x37 cm. The first part bears a three-line-inscription carved in ancient Greek. The inscription is well preserved and legible. The A is broken bar; the K has small ears.

Findspot: In front of the arch, on the pavement of the main street.

Dimensions: h.: 157 cm; d.: ca. 80 (top) cm; l.h.: 2.5-3 cm.

Date: I-IInd cent. A.D. (from the lettering).

Εναδι Ογωλλιος
2 Ὀρέστης Ἴέρωνος
τῆς γυναικί.

Orestes, son of Hieron, (set this up) for his wife Enas, daughter of Ogollis.

L. 1: The female name *Enas* is known from Cibyra, see *IKibyra* 212, 219 and 266 and Zgusta 1964 §334-3. According to the latest studies of T. Corsten there are also two new records from Kibyra and its territory. An *Enas* is recorded as the mother of Rhetorikos and other is recorded in dative case as *Εναδει*, see *LGPN VC*. The other name, *Ogollis* (Ογωλλίς, gen. -ιος), is known from the Roman treaty inscription found at Cibyra, as the father's name of Moagetes, one of the dynasts⁴, see also Zgusta 1964 §1070.

L. 2: The name *Orestes* has been attested at Kibyra thirteen times, see *IKibyra* 11, 38, 44E, 53, 71, 143, 162, 212, 298-299, 300-301, 336, and see *LGPN VC*. The name *Hieron* has also previously been recorded at Cibyra, see *IKibyra* 62-63, 191, 122-123, 212-219, 237, 254, 267-268, 308, 317, 319, 327, 345, 349.

4. A Fragmentary Epitaph

A cylindrical epitaph made of marble. The findspot is unknown. It was brought to the excavation house from the garden of Governmental building of the province in Gölhisar. The top is cut flat, and there is no sign of a hole. However, the front upper part, including three lines of the four-line-inscription has largely been broken off and is missing. The body is divided into three parts as in the first three stelae, in sizes ordered from top to bottom, 24 x 26 x 30 cm. There are fractures to the body. The letter sigma is written as a square C.

Findspot: Garden of Governmental building of the province in Gölhisar .

Dimensions: h.: 105 cm; d.: 0.60 m; l.h.: 3 cm.

Date: II-IIIrd cent. A.D. (from the lettering).

⁴ Özüdoğru 2018, 754.

Σ[-----]η
 2 τῆ μητρι] μνή-
 μης ἔνεκεν.

S... (set this up)
 for his/her mother NN,
 in memory.

L. 1: There must be two names, one of which starts with *sigma* (S) can be either female or male. The other is a female name in the dative case regarding the word τῆ μητρι] (for mother). Since there is no surviving indication of another letter from the first line those names cannot be known.

5. Epitaph of Troilos

A cylindrical epitaph carved from limestone. It was found on the western side of the odeium. The stele stands today in the stone field in front of the theatre. The top is high and flat, about 9 cm, the upper and lower parts are profiled. The front and right upper part is largely broken. There are some small broken parts on the lower part of the profiled area. The body is mostly fractured. The stele carries four lines of inscription which is mostly eroded but still remains legible.

Findspot: Western side of the odeium.

Dimensions: h.: 115 cm; d.: ca. 58 cm; l.h.: 3 cm.

Date: IInd cent. A.D. (from the *omega*).

Ἱέρων καὶ Παν-
 2 κράτης Τρωΐλω^{vv} β'
 καλῶ πατρι
 4 μνήμης ἔ^{vv}νεκα.

Hieron and Pankrates
 (set this up) for their
 noble father Troilos the second,
 in memory.

LL. 1-2: For the name *Pankrates* see above no 2, and for *Hieron* see above no 3.

L. 2: The name *Troilos* has previously been recorded at Cibyra, see *IKibyra* 254, 347, 350-351.

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